

1 USER INTERFACE FOR BLOCKCHAIN-BASED EPR PROTOTYPE

This section presents the interface implemented in the Application Layer for interacting with the different system users and their responsibilities.

1.1 Health Entities View

Users of this solution related to health Health Entities (HE), i.e., Health Professional (PS), Health Institution (HI), and Medical Laboratory (ML), must fill in their information in their respective registration forms in the system, as shown in Figures 1 and 2.

Figura 1 – Registration View of PS.

The screenshot shows a web interface for registering a health professional. At the top, there is a blue header with the text 'Prontuário Eletrônico do Paciente' on the left and 'Login Cadastrar' on the right. Below the header is a form titled 'Cadastrar Profissional da Saúde'. The form is organized into three main sections:

- Dados Pessoais:** Includes fields for 'Nome' and 'E-mail', a date picker for 'Data de Nascimento' (format dd/mm/aaaa), a dropdown for 'Gênero' (with 'Selecione' as the placeholder), and another dropdown for 'Estado Civil' (with 'Selecione' as the placeholder). Below these are fields for 'CPF', 'RG', and 'Telefone'.
- Endereço:** Includes a 'CEP' field, and a row with 'Logradouro', 'Número', and 'Bairro' fields. Below that is a row with 'Cidade', 'Estado', and 'País' fields.
- Dados Profissionais:** Includes fields for 'Profissão', 'Nº de Reg. no Conselho', and 'Data de Registro' (with a date picker in dd/mm/aaaa format).

Fonte: Elaborated by the author.

The user logged into the system can register different medical records for a patient. In the 'Register Report' section, the registration options are presented. The

Figura 2 – Registration Screen of and .

The image shows a web form for registering a health institution. The form is titled "Cadastrar Instituição de Saúde" and is part of the "Prontuário Eletrônico do Paciente" system. The form is organized into several sections:

- Dados da Instituição:** This section contains fields for "Nome", "E-mail", "CNPJ", "N° de Reg. no Conselho", and "Data de Registro". The "Data de Registro" field has a date picker icon.
- Endereço:** This section contains fields for "CEP", "Logradouro", "Número", "Bairro", "Cidade", "Estado", and "País".
- Dados do Responsável:** This section contains fields for "Nome", "CPF", and "Senha".

Fonte: Elaborated by the author.

form for each record contains fields based on some attributes required by FHIR for the resources, as presented in Section 3 of the manuscript.

Figure 3 shows the Anamnesis registration form, through which a series of questions regarding the patient's main complaint and medical history are asked. Figures 4, 5, and 6 demonstrate the registration of Observation, Exam, and Medication, respectively. The requested information in Observation refers to data such as vital signs that may indicate, for example, temperature and blood pressure, among other information. Exam registration indicates information from clinical tests, such as cholesterol, glucose, etc. Therefore, the test name and its respective value are requested. Specifically, the ML only has access to the registration of Exams among the types of records implemented. Finally, Medication registration refers to medications the PS or HI will prescribe for the patient. The user can enter information such as the name of the medication, method, dose, and observations.

Figura 3 – Anamnesis Registration Screen.

Prontuário Eletrônico do Paciente Home Registros Pacientes Registrar Laudo Olá, ▾

Registrar Anamnese

Identificação

ID do Paciente

História Doença Atual (HDA)

Qual a principal queixa?

Início dos sintomas e duração da queixa

Localização da dor

História Patológica Regressa

Está em tratamento médico com algum remédio?

Tem alguma alergia?

Cirurgia recente?

Alterações cardíacas (Cardiopatias)?

Fonte: Elaborated by the author.

Figura 4 – Observation Registration Screen.

Prontuário Eletrônico do Paciente Home Registros Pacientes Registrar Laudo Olá, ▾

Registrar Observação

ID do Paciente

Observações

1.

Fonte: Elaborated by the author.

Figura 5 – Exam Registration Screen.

Prontuário Eletrônico do Paciente Home Registros Pacientes Registrar Laudo Olá

Registrar de Diagnóstico

ID do Paciente

Data de Registro

dd/mm/aaaa

Testes

	Nome	Valor	Interpretação
1.			

ADICIONAR NOVO TESTE

Registrar Diagnóstico

Fonte: Elaborated by the author.

Figura 6 – Medication Registration Screen.

Prontuário Eletrônico do Paciente Home Registros Pacientes Registrar Laudo Olá

Registrar Medicação

ID do Paciente

Data de Registro

dd/mm/aaaa

Medicação

Remédio Método Dose

Observação

Registrar Medicação

Fonte: Elaborated by the author.

Besides the record registration functionalities, all types of HE can list all records of patients they have access to and the list of patients for whom the doctor has already submitted a medical record or any patient who has granted access to a particular record in their possession. In Figure 7, in the list of patients, each patient

is identified by their name, date of the last record, a button for more detailed patient information, and a button that directs to their specific records. In turn, in Figure 8, in the list of records of all patients, you can see the type of record, the name of the patient to whom the record belongs, date of the record, type of access, and a button that allows downloading the record.

Figura 7 – Patient List Screen.

Nome do Paciente	Último Registro	Informações do Paciente	Registros
João Silva	12/03/2021		

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Anterior 1 Próximo

Fonte: Elaborated by the author.

Figura 8 – Record Listing Screen.

Tipo de Registro	Nome Paciente	Data de Registro	Acesso	Registro
Anamnese	João Silva	2021-05-01 23:18:40	Liberado	
Observação	João Silva	2021-05-01 23:18:40	Liberado	

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Anterior 1 Próximo

Fonte: Elaborated by the author.

1.2 Patient View

Figure 9 shows the registration form used by the patient. All requested information is based on resource models derived from FHIR. Due to the implementation scope limitations of the PoC, and since there is a lot of suggested information, Figure 9 presents part of it.

Figura 9 – Patient Registration Screen.

Fonte: Elaborated by the author.

The user should be successfully registered by filling out all the information and clicking the registration confirmation. By accessing 'Login,' the user can enter their registered email credentials and passwords in the system. Once logged in, the menu will have the 'Records' option, as seen in Figure 10, where the user accesses their records already registered by a health entity. On this screen, besides the patient's listed records, the patient can control access to their medical information.

Figura 10 – Patient Records Screen.

Tipo de Registro	Data de Registro	Registro	Controle de Acesso	Médicos Autorizados
Anamnese	12/05/2020		✓ Liberar ✗ Negar	
Diagnóstico	12/06/2020		✓ Liberar ✗ Negar	

Fonte: Elaborated by the author.

It is possible to enter the identifier of the HE to authorize unauthorized access to the record by clicking on 'Allow' (button in green) or 'Deny' (button in red). Thus, the

record will be available in those authorized profiles and disabled if the patient withdraws access. Through the button in the 'Authorized Doctors' column, the user can view the list of HEs they have authorized to access a specific record, as seen in Figure 11.

Figura 11 – Authorized HE Screen.

Fonte: Elaborated by the author.

REFERÊNCIAS